

Special Relativity as the Root of Quantum Spin?

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It is well known that the formalism for spin $\frac{1}{2}$ appeared formally when Dirac linearized the Klein-Gordon equation: $EE = pp + m^2c^2$ with $E \rightarrow i\hbar \partial/\partial t$ and $p \rightarrow -i\hbar \partial/\partial x$. Nevertheless, Pauli already used 2×2 matrices linked to spin in the nonrelativistic form: $E = pp/2m + V(x)$. In particular: $p \cdot p = (\sigma \cdot p) (\sigma \cdot p)$ with σ being a vector of the three Pauli matrices. Finally, there is photon spin following from: $d/dt \text{ partial } (.5e_0 E \cdot E + .5/u_0 B \cdot B) + 1/u_0 \text{ grad dot } (E \times B)$ where E and B are electric and magnetic fields for a photon.

The point we wish to make is that all of these equations, relativistic or otherwise are relationships between energy and momentum. Thus, the first important question, we argue, is: Why should one be concerned with E and p and a relationship between the two? We suggest that if one considers a free particle or photon, and wishes to create $P(t)$ or $P(x)$, where P is probability, one requires a time interval or length. Traditionally, an artificial one is introduced, i.e. $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$, but we have argued previously that a natural one should exist. We suggested, based on the photon result: $x/t = c = E/p$ that x interval = constant/ p and t interval = constant/ E . In such a view, x and t are independent, but E and p are not. Not only are E and p key, but there should be a relationship between the two. The second question then becomes: What is this relationship and from where does it come?

We argue that for a particle with rest mass in the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ case, the relationship is $EE = pp + m^2c^2$ ($c=1$). This relationship becomes the nonrelativistic one: $E = pp/2m_0$ for $p \ll m_0$ where m_0 is rest mass. The key idea, we argue, is that $EE = pp + m^2c^2$ follows from special relativity. In particular, special relativity involves a Lorentz transformation from a (p, E) to a (p', E') through a matrix which is symmetric, but involves an unusual metric composed of the two row vectors $(1, 0)$, $(0, -1)$ in two dimensions. In other words, this matrix is at the heart of special relativity and special relativity is at the heart of the relationship between E and p which is key for defining probabilities in space and time, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ with natural lengths and intervals, constant/ p and constant/ E . As a result, we suggest that a matrix should appear in a quantum theory which is based on using a relationship between E and p , which is what is done in quantum mechanics. This matrix is called a spin matrix, but we argue that it has its roots in the Lorentz transformation matrix.

Free Particle $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$

We have noted that in the literature (1), classical spatial probability for a bound state is given by:

$$P(x)dx = Cdx/|v(x)| \text{ where } v(x) \text{ is velocity which follows from conservation of energy ((1))$$

In a bound problem there is a natural length, namely that between classical turning points, but for a free particle there is not. As a result, an artificial length L is introduced, i.e.

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \text{ for a free particle ((2))}$$

We have argued in previous notes that we think that one should have a natural length and time interval for a free particle and have suggested $\text{constant}/p$ and $\text{constant}/E$ by examining the photon relation:

$$C = x/t = E/p \quad ((3))$$

This may be generalized to a particle with rest mass. In order to have a result compatible with ((2)) we suggest:

$\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ and $\exp(-iEt)/\sqrt{L}$ ((4)) as dynamic probabilities.

At this point, there is no notion of spin whatsoever it seems.

A Relation For E and p

In the above, we treated t and x as independent and argued that one needs to introduce the dynamical variables E and p in order to create natural time and length intervals. E and p , however, are related and this relationship ultimately comes from special relativity, i.e.

$$E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 \quad (c=1) \quad \text{where } m_0 \text{ is rest mass} \quad ((5))$$

((5)), in the nonrelativistic limit yields $E = p^2/2m_0$ and for $m_0 = 0$, $E=pc$, the photon relation.

At this point, there is still no notion of spin. We note, however, that one may formally obtain $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ using $E \rightarrow -i\partial/\partial t$ partial and $p \rightarrow -i\partial/\partial x$ partial. These are generators of translation in time and space.

We suggest that one must consider the origins of ((5)), namely that it is a kind of dot product of the 4-vector (p, E) with itself. Given that one has a 4-vector, one also has a matrix which transforms this 4-vector as seen from different frames moving with different velocity values. Thus,

$$(p', E') = \text{Lorentz matrix} * (p, E). \quad ((6))$$

As a result, there is a specific (symmetric) matrix which transforms one set of p, E into another and this transformation is linked with a kind of rotation. We suggest that this transformation must be kept in mind when considering scalar equations such as ((5)). As an analogy, one may consider rotating a position vector r . Its magnitude is unchanged and $r \cdot r = r^2$, but the physics of rotation is still present. We suggest that the physics of a Lorentz transformation is still present in ((5)).

As a result, Dirac linearized ((5)) using $E=i\partial/\partial t$ partial and $p=-i\partial/\partial x$ partial and this led to a 4x4 matrix together with the operators d/dt and d/dx . The 4x4 matrix contains the 2x2 Pauli matrices.

A 4x4 matrix appears because one uses both d/dx and d/dt . In a nonrelativistic context with $E = \sqrt{p^2 + m_0^2}$, one may use the Pauli matrices alone to write:

$$\mathbf{p} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = (\mathbf{p} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}) (\mathbf{p} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}) \quad ((7))$$

Where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is a vector of Pauli matrices because $\sigma_i \sigma_j = \delta_{ij} + i \epsilon_{ijk} \sigma_k$ (no sum on i) and otherwise these anticommute.

The point is that in the linear form, a matrix appears because in the linear form (\mathbf{p}, E) is acted upon by a Lorentz transformation. In the energy relation, however, with d/dx and d/dt partial present, this matrix is now linked to something called spin, we argue. Our main point, however, is that due to a Lorentz matrix acting on (\mathbf{p}, E) one expects a matrix (related to rotation because the Lorentz matrix is also linked to a kind of rotation) if one linearizes an energy equation.

Why should one have an energy equation for a free particle in the first place? In the first section we were able to obtain $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ without an energy equation for a free particle. An energy equation, however, does exist and should be compatible with these results. It is and in fact brings in more physics, namely the notion of spin because (\mathbf{p}, E) transforms according to the Lorentz transformation (a kind of rotation).

The Photon Situation

In the case of the photon, one again has an expression linking energy density and momentum which leads to spin, i.e.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} (.5\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}) + \frac{1}{\mu_0} \text{grad} \cdot \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad ((8))$$

One may see again that one has a quadratic form in \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} and note that Maxwell's laws are compatible with special relativity. In this case, one may linearize ((8)) using:

$$\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B} = \epsilon_{ijk} E_j B_k \quad ((9))$$

In other words, ϵ_{ijk} becomes the spin matrix with j, k denoting the components. One may note that \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} do not transform as a Lorentz 4-vector, but (\mathbf{A}, ϕ) does and \mathbf{A}, ϕ is used to construct \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} through:

$$\mathbf{E} = -\text{grad} \phi - \frac{d\mathbf{A}}{dt} \text{partial} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{B} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{A} \quad ((10))$$

Thus, we again suggest that special relativity is linked to the idea that a rotation type matrix appears in ((2)) when one linearizes. It is already present in the form ((8)) through the cross product, but one wishes to have a linear expression in quantum mechanics upon which d/dt , d/dx and the spin matrix act, namely a wavefunction. In the photon case, $E + i\mathbf{B}$ becomes the wavefunction.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle may be found without any notion of spin. We note, however, that E and p appear and that there should be an equation linking them. We suggest that the idea of spin appears when one considers this equation whether it be: $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$, $E = \sqrt{p^2 + m^2}$ or the photon continuity equation ((8)). Furthermore, it only appears when one tries to linearize such an equation. (In the case of $E = \sqrt{p^2 + m^2}$, one tries to linearize p using Pauli matrices to remove the dot product, so that one has: $(\mathbf{p} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})$ $(\mathbf{p} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})$). We suggest that a spin matrix appearing when one linearizes, with spin being like a kind of rotation, is linked to the fact that a relation between E and p ultimately comes from special relativity, where the Lorentz matrix (which is a kind of rotation) acts on the 4-vector (p, E) .

In other words, in special relativity one sees a type of rotation vector acting on (p, E) and we suggest that the physics linked with this matrix appears when one takes an energy-momentum expression (which ultimately comes from special relativity) and linearizes it. In such a case, a rotation like matrix should appear which is linked to the Lorentz transformation we suggest.

References

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